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HONEY BEE ARTIFICIAL SELECTION IS A THREAT
FOR GENETIC DIVERSITY, IN CONTRAST TO NATURAL
AND DARWIN BLACK BOX SELECTION

La selezione artificiale dell'ape mellifera è una minaccia per la sua diversità genetica, in contrasto con la selezione naturale ed il concetto di Darwin black box

Targeted selection and domestication cause loss of genetic diversity and functional traits. Although western honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) have not yet been domesticated (OLDROYD, 2012), much efforts have been made to 'improve' the managed bee stock through artificial selection (GUICHARD *et al.*, 2020) and introgression or replacement of local with foreign subspecies (ESPREGUEIRA THEMUDO *et al.*, 2020). In order to imagine where the targeted selection road might take the honey bee, we looked at the effects of domestication on other animals. Fages *et al.* (2017, see citation in PANZIERA *et al.*, 2022) tracked six millennia of horse domestication, showing that for five millennia genetic diversity was conserved, with much local variation, but that in the latest millennium diversity losses increased due to intensive exchange. These losses culminated in the recent two centuries during which horse husbandry and selection became global and coordinated. Similarly, recent cattle breeds have a much smaller brain volume compared to their wild ancestor species, the level of brain volume loss positively correlating with the level of domestication (Balcarel *et al.*, 2021, citation in PANZIERA *et al.*, 2022). When domestic chicken feralised on an island, several 'wild' alleles became dominant, but the road back was not the same as the domestication road run, so the rewilded chicken differed from the original wild species (Johnson *et al.*, 2016, citation in PANZIERA *et al.*, 2022).

Honey bee genetic diversity is in swift decline in Europe and needs

protection. A comparison of genetic diversity of worker bees from Europe between the second half of the 20th century with that of 2013 showed a great decline (ESPREGUEIRA THEMUDO *et al.*, 2020), being caused by both (one-sided) artificial selection and by introduction of non-local bees. Moreover, TANASKOVIC *et al.* (2021, 2022) found a local subspecies from Serbia to be lost, due to preferential use of foreign breeds and large scale movement of colonies. Introduced colonies may also interfere with local adaptations in local bees, and interrupt genetic co-adaptations of bees and their biomes (both parasites and commensals, BLACQUIÈRE & PANZIERA, 2018). Wherever local populations of bees are present, be it wild or kept, invasion of non-local bees through breeding or movement of colonies should be prevented and mitigated by isolation zones (FONTANA *et al.*, 2018; REQUIER *et al.*, 2019), to allow genetic adaptation to proceed (NEUMANN & BLACQUIÈRE, 2017).

Varroa resilience needed now. *Varroa destructor* is presently the strongest threat for western beekeeping and honey bees in the wild (ROSENKRANZ *et al.*, 2010; TRAYNOR *et al.*, 2020). In beekeeping the Varroa mite is controlled, but this blocks any chance for selection of resilience (NEUMANN & BLACQUIÈRE, 2017). Several targeted selection programs have tried to increase resistance to the Varroa mite, but despite great emphasis so far with only limited success, whilst several cases have been described of populations of honey bees cohabiting with Varroa just by natural co-adaptation (see LE CONTE *et al.*, 2020). Note that natural selection is based on increasing fitness, at the level of the colony, and does conserve variation (including that of the biomes), as opposed to targeted selection which aims at selecting specific traits, on the level of the queens (MIKHEYEV *et al.*, 2015; KOVACIC *et al.*, 2020). Apart from Varroa resistance, many of the traits selected for in programs reduce fitness (docility, no swarming, low propolis use, queen fertility) at the colony level (PANZIERA *et al.*, 2022).

Selection and co-evolution alike in Nature: Darwins Black Box. In order to achieve resilience in the presence of Varroa mites without knowing how this might work (and so without knowing for which trait one should select), we designed the DBB protocol (BLACQUIÈRE *et al.*, 2019), and used it in several honey bee populations since 2007. The protocol is based on in-population natural selection for fitness (incl survivorship, colony growth, reproduction ability) without varroa control. After a few years a stable or increasing local population of colonies arises. From these populations one may learn how honey bee colonies are able to cohabit with Varroa, and which mechanisms may be involved. These will be highlighted in the talk of Delphine Panziera.

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